

D3.3: Communication Packages III

M22-M48

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock

Deliverable n°:	D3.3 (III)
Deliverable name:	Communication Packages III
Version:	3.0
Release date:	28/02/2023
Dissemination level:	Public
Status:	Final
Author:	Sidsel Bruun/GECO (Smart Innovation Norway)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.3	28/02/2023	Final version	Sidsel Bruun

Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
IEECP	Marine Perrio

Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
All consortium partners

Table of contents

Executive summary	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Policy-oriented materials	7
2.1 Policy brief	7
2.2 Visual summary of strategies for rolling out P4P schemes in the EU	7
2.3 Policy session at the SENSEI Final Conference	8
2.4 Recommendations to policymakers	8
3 Summary presentations	8
3.1 Summary presentation	8
3.2 SENSEI Briefing	8
3.3 Booklet: Metered energy savings and pay-for-performance schemes: Why now?	9
3.4 Graphic recordings	9
3.5 Explainer videos	10
3.6 Project video	10
3.7 Pay-for-Performance elearning tool	11
4 Research papers, outcomes and deliverables	13
4.1 Scientific papers	13
4.2 Deliverables presenting research results	15
4.3 The eensight M&V tool	19
4.4 E-book: Rethinking Measurement and Verification of Energy Savings	19
5 Conclusion	20

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
Tx.y	Task number

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Executive summary

The present deliverable contains a brief overview to the relevant dissemination and communication materials produced and published during the H2020 funded SENSEI project, including links to the material. The deliverable answers to *T3.3: Communication Packages* and is the last of three Communication Packages produced in the SENSEI project. [D3.3 \(I\)](#) and [D3.3 \(II\)](#) have been published, reporting on materials published previously. The deliverable describes the policy-oriented communication materials, the summary presentations available and, a list and links to public deliverables and scientific papers.

1 Introduction

This deliverable provides an overview and an introduction to the communication and dissemination materials developed as part of the Horizon 2020 funded EU project SENSEI, with a particular focus on the last project period (M22-M48) as D3.3 (I) and D3.3 (II) are reporting on previous Communication Packages. The deliverable answers to the third Communication Package in Task 3.3 which includes *“a policy brief, and a summary presentation to recap the key findings and results tailored for the project partners’ own use enabling them to exploit the project work post-SENSEI. The final communication package will also include a video (scribing techniques), which documents the results of the project”*. Hence, we introduce the communication and dissemination material stated in the Grant Agreement. However, as SENSEI has in the final project period developed important additional communication materials to support the exploitation of project results and increase awareness and knowledge, they will also be introduced as an important source of information to interested stakeholders.

The material presented here should first and foremost be regarded as a guide for consortium partners to continue the dissemination and exploitation of results beyond the project duration. As such, this document provides an overview of the available communication and dissemination materials on the research and knowledge developed through SENSEI about the potential, drivers and barriers to implementing Pay-for-Performance programmes in the European Union to increase investments in energy efficiency refurbishment projects. It is important to stress that this deliverable do not provide a complete overview of the communication, dissemination and engagement activities performed in SENSEI. A full overview is available in the confidential *D2.2: Interim progress reports on the stakeholder consultation process (III)*.

Chapter 2 gives an overview of materials to support communication and dissemination efforts directed to e.g., policymakers.

Chapter 3 lists available presentations to help consortium partners communicate project results.

Chapter 4 provides an overview of scientific papers and publications.

2 Policy-oriented materials

With policymakers being a key stakeholder category for the SENSEI project, robust material has been produced to support the communication to this group, and disseminated through various means (global and targeted emails, social media, etc.).

2.1 Policy brief

Communication Package (II) included a [policy brief](#), providing background information on Pay-for-Performance schemes and recommendations on how legislators could improve the EU climate and energy framework and put pay-for-performance schemes at the service of the EU's Renovation Wave. The brief was distributed on social media, the SENSEI website and the newsletter.

2.2 Visual summary of strategies for rolling out P4P schemes in the EU

Based on the report *DB.1: Policy developments in the European Union and strategies for Pay-for-Performance business models*, a visual summary was designed presenting the 10 strategies identified for rolling out P4P schemes in the EU (see Figure 1). This is available on the website under [Communication Materials](#) and was disseminated by the project and partners in various channel: social media, newsletters, etc.

Figure 1: Strategies for rolling-out P4P schemes in the EU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

2.3 Policy session at the SENSEI Final Conference

The first session of the SENSEI Final Conference, organised January 24, 2023 in Brussels (and online) provides key insights into the regulatory adaptations needed to support increased energy efficiency refurbishments. [Recordings of this session](#) (and the other two) are available on YouTube, as well as a graphic recording design.

2.4 Recommendations to policymakers

Under the leadership of SENSEI, the group of sister projects prepared and submitted a letter with policy recommendations for buildings in the energy transition to EU policymakers and stakeholders. The letter is available at [Zenodo](#).

3 Summary presentations

To support consortium partners in further communication activities, this chapter gives an overview of available summary presentations, in addition to the PowerPoint templates available at the SENSEI SharePoint.

3.1 Summary presentation

To support the partners in presenting the Pay-for-Performance concept, a PowerPoint presentation has been designed with slides explaining the concept and the potential for implementing in the European Union. The presentation is available at the SENSEI drive, so partners can download and use, also after the project ends. This does not entail an overview of all project activities, but a summary of important results.

3.2 SENSEI Briefing

A visual 2-pager with a project briefing was designed to support communication on project objectives and results. It is [available on the website](#) and can be seen in Figure 2 below. It was designed by IEECP following a lunch seminar with a short introduction to IEECP projects to the team, then loaded to YouTube and widely shared.

SENSEI
Pay-For-Performance Schemes in Europe

Briefing
This briefing presents the motivations behind the SENSEI project as well as the advantages of Pay-For-Performance, and why energy efficiency is more important than ever in Europe amidst the current energy crisis and Russian tensions.

What is Pay-for-Performance?
Pay-for-Performance (P4P) is an innovative approach to invest energy efficiency when payments are linked to the measured performance. P4P can be started:

- Improve subsidy schemes with periodic payments that are proportional to measured energy savings, using advanced Measurement and Verification (M&V) software.
- Aggregate projects into portfolios to attract investment from financial institutions that are looking to invest in larger projects.
- Recognize energy efficiency as a demand-side energy resource to optimising its benefits for the energy system.

Benefits & Challenges

Benefits:

- An effective way to engage in energy efficiency projects for **third-party investors and energy providers**, which channels larger amounts of financing.
- Avoids the need for technical upgrades.
- Participation in capacity auctions as **demand side energy source**.
- Optimisation of energy efficiency programmes through **deeper savings**.

Challenges that can be overcome with P4P:

- **Lack of investment** in building stock and private sector; financial institutions are attracted to low transaction and administrative costs for large projects with copassant and long term cash flow.
- **Strong misalignment of incentives** since investments are made with almost no accountability in terms of energy savings.

Concrete example of P4P Scheme

The aggregator gathers financing from financial institutions and channels it to renovations, while a system operator rewards the aggregator for reducing the overall demand.

RENNOVATION WAVE
The Renovation Wave is an EU Green Deal priority and pushes the renovation of existing buildings. The Commission invites the market to pilot P4P schemes to boost renovations.

SENSEI's role in P4P
The project investigates P4P in the US to aggregate retrofit projects and improves the effectiveness of subsidy programmes. This enables to provide energy efficiency as an energy resource and service to the grid.

Examples of advancements in Measurement and Verification techniques

- SENSEI's **sensight tool** will provide essential insights for investors, energy companies, legislators and building owners.
- **IPMVP**, International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol.
- **CALTRACK** process of arriving at a calculation of avoided energy use.

Necessary steps to pilot P4P schemes in Europe

1. Secure high level commitments (Political, System Operators) to pilot energy efficiency programmes based on Pay-For-Performance and metered savings.
2. Designate a competent managing authority (i.e. an energy agency) to oversee and support the co-design and execution of pilots.
3. Adopt a transparent methodology for metered savings using measurement and verification methods such as CalTRACK or sensight to increase accuracy and transparency.
4. Issue tenders for energy efficiency projects that adopt the Pay-For-Performance approach and a compensation structure based on metered savings.
5. Gather insights and good practices from the first pilots, conduct capacity building activities, and repeat piloting with improved refinements.

Interested? Already involved in a similar scheme?
Reach out to: info@sensei2020.eu

The SENSEI project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 847066.

Figure 2: SENSEI Briefing page 1 and 2

3.3 Booklet: Metered energy savings and pay-for-performance schemes: Why now?

[This booklet](#) sets the context for the relevance and importance of prioritizing initiatives to increase investments in demand efficiency refurbishment projects, for instance through innovative business schemes such as Pay-for-Performance programmes. It was developed towards the project end to be distributed mainly at events and at the final conference. Additionally available online, it was thought as an easy-to-read guidebook.

3.4 Graphic recordings

The presentations and debate at the final event of SENSEI (hosted on 24 January 2023 in Brussels and online with available recordings [here at YouTube](#)) were captured by a professional graphic recorder in 3 illustrations, one per panel debate. These illustrations are also [available for download](#) at the SENSEI website and can be used during presentations and discussions on the Pay-for-Performance concept. For an example, see Figure 3 below.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Figure 3: Graphic recordings, Introduction at SENSEI Final Conference

3.5 Explainer videos

To improve the dissemination of the Pay-for-Performance concept, a series of short explainer videos have been produced. The different aspects of the concept and business models are explained in a step by step format. The videos are available with subtitles in 9 European languages; [English](#), [Greek](#), [Spanish](#), [Catalan](#), [Danish](#), [German](#), [French](#), [Dutch](#) and, [Italian](#). These videos can be integrated in presentations and used by partner organisations to promote and explain the concept. Example messages for each video and how to post them on social media were shared with partners and are available in the SENSEI drive.

3.6 Project video

In addition to the [first project video](#) introducing the Pay-for-Performance concept, produced as part of the first Communication Package, a second video has been produced as part of the third Communication Package. While the first video was a short introduction to the Pay-for-Performance concept, the second official project video offers an overview of project results in a comprehensive and graphic way. As well as introducing the renewed understanding of Pay-for-Performance in a European context, it introduces the eensight measurement and verification tool, the role of the energy efficiency aggregator and a five-step-approach to introducing Pay-

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

for-Performance in the EU. The [second video](#) is available on the SENSEI YouTube channel and was added on the website homepage (see screenshot below).

3.7 Pay-for-Performance elearning tool

The EngageSuite elearning platform provides practical information for those interested in knowing more about the details of Pay-for-Performance schemes, and the SENSEI model in particular. The content of the platform is organized so as to present the concept to four key stakeholder groups:

- Building owners,
- Energy providers,
- ESCOs and
- Policy makers.

The platform offers 4 streams of knowledge, tailored to provide information for members of each stakeholder category to understand what P4P is for them. It sketches the incentives for that particular group for getting involved in a P4P scheme, the requirements, responsibilities and tasks that are entailed (see screenshot in Figure 4 for an example). But the content is also relevant for others wanting to get a fuller grasp of what P4P means in practice and what it entails for key stakeholder groups.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the ESCO track at the elearning platform

To ease the promotion of the elearning tool, a flyer has been designed, [available at the website](#) for print (A5 format recommended) or to be sent online. See front and back page in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: SENSEI elearning tool, flyer page 1 and 2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

4 Research papers, outcomes and deliverables

4.1 Scientific papers

The research activities of SENSEI are presented in 3 peer-reviewed scientific papers with one more submitted and currently under peer-review and 2 scientific papers published in conference proceedings. These are listed in Table 1 which provides link to the open research databases.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

Title	Outlet & Link	Date	Readers	Citations
Peer-reviewed scientific journals				
<i>A review of deterministic and data-driven methods to quantify energy efficiency savings and to predict retrofitting scenarios in buildings</i>	Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews	Oct. 2020	204	38
<i>A data-driven methodology for enhanced measurement and verification of energy efficiency savings in commercial buildings</i>	Applied Energy Volume 301, 1 November 2021,	Nov. 2021	71	11
<i>Pioneering a performance-based future for energy efficiency: Lessons learnt from a comparative review analysis of pay-for-performance programmes</i>	Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews Volume 158, April 2022	April 2022	45	4
<i>Devising policy strategies for the deployment of energy efficiency Pay-for-Performance programmes in the European Union</i>	Energy Policy	Under peer review. Submitted on 11 May 2022		
Conference proceedings				

<i>Devising Classes of Energy Efficiency Measure for Evaluating Pay-4-Performance Rate That Energy Provider Will Be Willing to Offer in Pay-4-Performance Scheme</i>	The 8th Annual International Sustainable Places Conference (SP2020)	Dec. 2020	524	0
<i>Energy efficiency directive 3.0: Can “metered savings” approaches support EU’s Renovation Wave objectives?</i>	ecee Summer Study 2021 Proceedings	June 2021	50*	8*

Table 1: List of scientific publications

4.2 Deliverables presenting research results

The research is also disseminated in deliverables. These are all available for download and citation in the Pay-for-Performance community at zenodo.org. A list of all public deliverables is available in Table 2.

Title	Summary
D1.3: KPI and impact assessment	This deliverable will be uploaded to the SENSEI pay-for-performance community at the Zenodo platform upon finalisation.
D1.5: Final Publishable Report	This deliverable will be uploaded to the SENSEI pay-for-performance community at the Zenodo platform upon finalisation.
D3.2: Project website and social media presence	SENSEI Website , LinkedIn profile , Twitter profile and YouTube Channel . The website will stay live until 28-09-2025. IECCP, as project coordinator, will also duplicate the main contents and results on its website, to ensure they are exploited on a longer run.
D3.3: Communication Packages	The deliverable presents a summary of relevant communication material including links, to be utilised by consortium partners.
D3.5: Consolidated content for the SENSEI stakeholder support activities	The content is presented on the SENSEI P4P Knowledge Platform .
D3.6: Online SENSEI knowledge dissemination platform	The SENSEI P4P Knowledge Platform is available online.
D4.1: Opportunities and requirements for monetizing energy efficiency as an energy resource in EU	This report examines the mechanisms that are in place in the United States (U.S.) and Europe to reward energy efficiency as an energy system resource and draws conclusions for the focus of future efforts in the European Union (EU).

D4.2: The drivers of the value of energy efficiency as an energy resource	This deliverable proposes a methodology to quantify the value of an energy efficiency improvement project or a portfolio of such projects, as a power grid resource.
D4.3: The boundary cases for the P4P rates with Annex: Classes of Energy Efficiency Measures	This report provides a concrete classification and evaluation of the various EEMs which provides the foundations for proposing a definition of a P4P rate that is transparent and a non-performance-based incentive that can be offered to energy provider and, it identifies the market value of energy savings from the energy providers' perspective.
D4.4: Experience and lessons learned from P4P pilots for energy efficiency	This report aims to review the current experience of Pay-for-Performance (P4P) schemes outside the EU, in particular with examples from the U.S. (11 in total) as well as one case from the EU (Germany), and to document the main enablers and obstacles for the roll-out of the first P4P pilots in the EU
D5.2: Guidelines for the design of P4P schemes	This report aims at formulating guidelines for designing a pay-for-performance (P4P) programme that steers towards energy efficiency measures in buildings benefiting both building owners and the power system.
D5.3: Guidelines for the design of effective P4P rate structures	This report aims to identify the relationship between the compensation rate structures within a P4P scheme and the required energy efficiency measures of a group of selected buildings.
D5.4: The interplay between P4P and demand response incentives	This deliverable identifies how a P4P scheme can incentivise the implementation of energy efficiency measures that also improve demand flexibility potential.
D6.1: The SENSEI methodology for the ex-ante evaluation of the financial benefits	Energy retrofits of buildings have for long been known to deliver more benefits than solely energy cost savings. The report describes a methodology for the monetization of these 'multiple benefits'.

D6.3: Variants of P4P schemes to engage third party investors in energy efficiency	This deliverable focuses primarily on the public financial stakeholders' view with respect to funding payment for performance (P4P) programmes in the EU.
D6.4: Proposal on the specifications for P4P project data	This report is aimed at defining a list of indicators that can be used to evaluate the impact of implemented Pay-for-Performance (P4P) programs for energy efficiency
D6.5: The business model of the energy efficiency aggregator	The EE Aggregator and P4P programmes are being explored in the context of the Renovation Wave for meeting the EU's energy efficiency targets using innovative financing and new business models.
D7.1: Methods for the dynamic M&V of energy savings	By offering a new, advanced energy efficiency metering tool named eensight, this deliverable aims at contributing to the advancement of the automated measurement and verification (M&V) methods for energy efficiency
D7.2: Web-based demonstrations of the integrated P4P and EPC model	This document is a reference to navigate through the web tools developed within the project, particularly the SENSEI platform and its smart services. The information is aimed at final, nontechnical users.
D7.3: Data models and service interfaces for the SENSEI smart services	This deliverable summarizes the used methodological approach to develop interoperable Smart Energy Services, to improve energy efficiency of European building stock, as well as to draw conclusions for P4P programmes.
D7.4: Functional design options for the SENSEI smart services	This deliverable aims at describing the SENSEI platform from a perspective that illustrates how the smart services developed in the project can be implemented in a real scenario and used by different actors.

D8.1: Policy developments in EU and strategies for P4P business models	This report focuses on ways that policy and regulatory developments in the EU may become risks or opportunities for P4P schemes. In particular, the main goal of this study is to analyse the directives, policies and measures already adopted, as well as those under consideration by the EU.
D8.2: Consolidated services and technical standards catalogue	Within this deliverable from the SENSEI project, an overview of meaningful ‘smart’ technologies in the context of buildings is given in a so-called service catalogue acting as a single source for an overview of technologies in the context of smart buildings actively contributing to the KPI of a Smart Readiness Indicator.
D8.3: Governance models and P4P acceptance	This deliverable will be uploaded to the SENSEI pay-for-performance community at the Zenodo platform upon finalisation.

Table 2: List of public deliverables

4.3 The eesight M&V tool

The eesight tool is a next-generation machine learning tool that will contribute to the much-needed advancement of automated measurement and verification methods for energy efficiency. It will provide essential insights for investors, energy companies, legislators and building owners. It is publicly available on github.com with an instructional video on [YouTube](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...). This open access tool allows researchers and industry to lay the foundation for energy efficiency project aggregation schemes and/or energy efficiency support programs by providing the insights that are necessary for all parties involved in up-scaling energy efficiency to correctly evaluate risks and expected benefits.

4.4 E-book: Rethinking Measurement and Verification of Energy Savings

In the scope of SENSEI, the e-book [Rethinking Measurement and Verification of Energy Savings](#) authored by Sotiris Papadelis (HEBES Intelligence) has been published. The book presents in details the SENSEI methodology for measurement and verification of energy savings in a P4P programme. The methodology has some unique characteristics that make it appropriate for P4P

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 847066.

applications: (a) it ignores changes in energy consumption that can be accounted for by changes in activity/occupancy levels, (b) it can deal with intermittent energy consumption where we cannot easily predict when energy consumption is going to be larger than zero, and (c) it can adapt to changes in the intensity of energy consumption, such as, for example, when fewer people use the building due to restrictions imposed to deal with the COVID 19 pandemic. The e-book also shows how the SENSEI methodology is implemented using the open source eensight tool. The target groups are ESCOs and EPC facilitators, as well as designers of P4P programmes.

5 Conclusion

Because SENSEI is the first project investigating the Pay-for-Performance programme in a European context, it is important that this research stay available as it is currently the only source of knowledge. This deliverable has presented the available communication and dissemination materials developed in the last project period. The material is available on the project website (www.senseih2020.eu) which will stay live until September 2025, after which IEECP as the coordinator will ensure that the main content is available on their website. All video material is also available on the YouTube channel and will stay there more permanently. As for the research results presented in project deliverables, these are uploaded to the Zenodo platform and will stay there also after the website closes.

